

A RELATIVE STUDY OF PHYSICAL FITNESS AMONG KHO-KHO AND KABADDI FEMALE PLAYERS

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ABSTRACT

Fitness is an individual matter which implies the ability of each person to live more potentiality and effectively. It is a general state of health and well-being and, more specifically, the ability to perform aspects of sports, occupant ions and daily activities. Physical fitness is generally achieved through proper nutrition, moderate-vigorous physical exercise and sufficient rest. Effective living depends upon the physical, mental, emotional, social and spiritual components of fitness. The term physical fitness means more than muscular strength and stamina; it implies efficient performance in exercise or work and a reasonable means of skill in the performance of selected physical activities. It is a measure of the body's ability to function efficiently and effectively in work and leisure activities, to be healthy, to resist hypokinetic diseases, and to meet emergency situations. Physical fitness and good health appear to be almost synonymous, but they are not exactly so; a man who is healthy may not be physically fit. The amount of required physical fitness differs from one occupation to another. Physical activity has important implications for the health and well being of all individuals. Easy life has negatively influenced the development and maintenance of physical fitness.

Key Words: *Potentiality, Moderate-Vigorous, Components, Synonymous, Implications etc.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Physical activity and physical fitness these two are closely related with each other, although not entirely, determined by physical activity patterns over recent weeks or months. A Genetic contribution for fitness is important but probably account for less of the variation observed in fitness than is due to environmental factors, principally physical activity. Fitness means many things—Strength, Vigor, Capacity for work, Vitality etc, fitness is a very wide term to be viewed and to understand it in broad perspective. Fitness generally implies

Soundness and readiness for life, and its functions. There are many special kinds of fitness for certain behaviors (sport, exercise, play) which resulting in physical fitness referring to its specific nature and life situations. Physical fitness is the capacity to meet successfully the present and potential physical challenges of life.

Physical fitness is the body's ability to function comprehensively and perfectly in the day to day life to be healthy for the betterment of one's life and others. Life is precious and should be given the tonic of fitness. To be physically fit one should perform daily exercises and take proper diet. Physical fitness is a physiological state of well-being that provides the foundation for the tasks of daily living, the degree for the protection against chronic disease and a basis for participation in sport. In crux, physical fitness describes a set of attributes relating to how well one performs physical activity.

2. IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL FITNESS

I. Overall Health

A regular fitness routine helps in improve your overall health and the positive effects become very evident when you invest time exercise. An energetic walk for 30 plus minute and some basic resistance training is all you need to get the ball rolling. This will get blood circulating, burns those pesky calories, and improves immunity... who doesn't need an elevated immune system. The basic take away? Be consistent!

II. Boosts Energy

Just about all of us could use a boost in the energy department! If this sounds like something you'd be interested in, you'll see what we mean after you feel the difference from a simple workout out, or after a good cardio session. You'll also feel rejuvenated and energized throughout the day. Contrary to this, if your lifestyle is sedentary, you will feel tired and sluggish... not good. Therefore, be intentional about being active and get fit doing it! A win-win situation for sure.

III. Weight Reduction

Dropping pounds is the one of the primary advantages of being fit. Working out regularly simply gets the fat burning fire roaring, and with time, you will see the noticeable difference. This is obviously rhetorical – we know what we *should* be doing to stay fit, but we all need a reminder from time to time. You can burn extra calories by simply getting yourself moving, which is definitely healthy for the body. In doing so, you start to see the numbers game – calories in vs. calories out – take affect on your body composition. Keep this up over time and you will like what you see and how you feel . Therefore, weight reduction is one of the important benefits of physical fitness.

IV. Strong Build

Staying fit with regular workouts and resistance training makes your bones strong. Additionally, people suffering from back issues, shoulder pain, etc. must be regular with certain exercises... Just ask your Physical Therapist! If you diligently follow a program, the pain is bound to reduce. Properly increasing muscle strength throughout your body also lends itself to better posture, joint support, muscle balance and it will increase your overall metabolic rate, which will effectively cause your body to naturally burn more calories throughout the day. All are great side effects!

V. Mental Strength

A fit body is not only physically strong but mentally strong a well. A routine that includes proper exercise and diet has a positive effect on brain function as well. It elevates blood flow to brain and enhances one's brain function.

VI. Personality Development

Staying fit helps keep you looking good! The more you indulge yourself in to healthy habits, the more you improve your overall look. This increases your confidence level and transcends to your overall disposition and self image. You feel fresh, you have a spring in your step, and you feel rejuvenated throughout the day. Your mood remains happy and optimistic too. Win!

VII. Be Inspired

I hope more folks can grasp why is fitness important... it simply transcends all aspects of our life in one way or another. Transforming your lifestyle can make all the difference in the world and it is almost never too late to take the first step. If you have more questions on health, fitness and overall wellness, let us help inspire you to achieve a level of fitness that will server you for the rest of your life! You got this.

3. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study will be delimited as following:-

- The study will be delimited to purposively select 100 female subjects age ranging from 18 to 23 years of Senior Colleges of Sangli City, participated at Inter-Zonal and School National (SGFI) Kabaddi and Kho-Kho competition.
- The study will be delimited to 100 female players at schools levels and 50 female players of Kabaddi and 50 female kho-kho players.
- The investigation will be delimited to selected physical variables as under:-

1. Physical

a. Height

b. Body weight

c. BMI

2. Physical Fitness Components

a. Speed- 40m. Sprint

b. Explosive Strength- standing broad jump

c. Cardiovascular endurance- 12min. run/walk test

d. Coordinative ability- 4X10m. = 40m. Shuttle run

e. Flexibility- Sit/bend and reach test

4. LIMITATIONS

The findings of the study will be understood by considering the following limitations.

- ❖ Availability of small number of sample size will be one of the limitations of the study.
- ❖ Sophisticated testing equipment and sophisticated equipment for exercises will also be one of the limitations for the present study.
- ❖ Individual differences among the subjects and other factors such as- Life Style, dietary habits, daily routine, will also considered limitations for the present study.

5. METHODS

For the purpose of the study one hundred players- 50 from the game of Kabaddi and 50 from the Kho-Kho has been selected on purposively and randomly basis, who has won medal/ position in Inter-Zonal and participated in State Level Games during the 2014 to 2017. All the subjects were regularly practicing and competing in their respective sports competition. Health and Physical Education is defined as the process by which individuals and groups of people learn to behave in a manner conducive to the promotion, maintenance or restoration of health. It is a continuing process of informing people how to achieve and maintain good health; of motivating them to do so; and of promoting environmental and lifestyle changes to facilitate their objective. The research scholar gleaned through all the scientific literature pertaining to Kabaddi and Khokho from books, magazines, journals, periodicals available in the various libraries of Vijayapura and internet surfing/sites. Keeping the feasibility criterion in mind, especially in the case of availability of instruments, the following physical abilities were selected i.e. Body Mass Index (BMI), Speed, Standing Broad Jump, Sit and Reach, Sit-Ups, 12minutes Run/walk

6. DISCUSSION

The significant difference was found in the Body Mass Index- in relation to the Kabaddi and Kho-Kho players. The Kabaddi players group was have more BMI showing greater body mass than the Kho-Kho players group. The significant difference was found in the speed ability- 40m sprint test the Kho-Kho players group had better speed in comparison to the Kabaddi players group. The significant difference was found in the Standing Broad Jump a test of explosive strength in relation to the Kabaddi and Kho-Kho players. The Kabaddi players group had high explosive strength, showing greater jumping ability than the Kho-Kho players group. The significant difference was found in the Sit and Reach test in the Kho-Kho players group had better hips and legs flexibility in comparison to the Kabaddi players group. The significant difference was found in the 1 minute Sit-Ups test of muscular strength endurance in relation to the Kabaddi and Kho-Kho players. The Kabaddi players group had better muscular strength endurance of abdomen muscles group, showing greater muscular endurance ability than the Kho-Kho players group. The significant difference was found in the 12minutes Run/Walk test of cardiovascular endurance in relation to the Kabaddi and Kho-Kho players. The Kho-Kho players group had better cardiovascular endurance, showing greater heart and lungs capacity than the Kabaddi players group.

7. CONCLUSION

Physical fitness includes more than muscular strength. He further enunciates that physical fitness implies soundness of the body organs such as heart and lungs, a human mechanism that perform efficiently under exercise or work conditions, and reasonable measure of performance in selected physical activities.

Physical fitness includes those qualities which will permit an individual to perform life activities involving speed, strength, agility, power and endurance and to engage in various kinds of physical activities required of modern-day living including sports and athletics, and to be able to maintain optimum amount of fitness for the individual involve

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